

JOB CONTRACTORS' EFFICIENCY AND PRODUCTIVITY OF SELECTED QUICK-SERVICE RESTAURANTS IN LAGUNA

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative causal (regression) research study aimed was to determine the level of job contractors' efficiency and the level of productivity in selected QSRs in Laguna. The incidental sampling method identified 74 respondents based on a 0.361 effect size with 95% level of confidence through G*Power from the managers of QSRs. Researcher-made questionnaires were used to gather data based on the mentioned theories. These had a Lawshe's Content Validity Ratio of 1.00 and Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of 0.943 for job contractors' efficiency and 0.964 for QSRs' productivity. Frequency, Four-Point Likert Scale, Mean, Pearson's r, and Regression Analysis were used to analyze the data. The study found that job contractors' efficiency was rated as Efficient, with turnover rate, job satisfaction, and labor cost having means of 3.05, 3.19, and 2.97, respectively. Managers assessed the productivity level of QSRs as Efficient in terms of responsiveness, quality of work, and cost-effectiveness, with means of 3.03, 3.08, and 3.07, respectively. Significant relationships were identified, with probability values of .000, all below the significance level of $P < 0.05$. Turnover rates and labor costs impacted responsiveness, with probability values of .005 and .000, respectively. Job satisfaction and labor costs influenced the quality of work, with probability values of .006 and .000, respectively. Labor costs affected cost-effectiveness, with a probability value of .000, all of which were less than the level of significance at $P < 0.05$. To further enhance efficiency and productivity, the study proposed a training and development program for job contractors' team leaders.

Keywords: *Job Contractors' Efficiency, Productivity, Turnover rate, Labor Cost, Job Satisfaction, Responsiveness, Quality of Work, Cost-effectiveness*

INTRODUCTION

Quick-service restaurants serve as a significant contributor to job creation worldwide, offering employment opportunities to a diverse international labor force with varied cultures and preferences. Sustaining profitability while meeting customer preferences for food quality and efficient service demands adept management capabilities. This includes compliance with diverse government regulatory requirements across different operational jurisdictions.

Exquisite leadership skills are imperative while fostering innovation essential for team development and maintaining the brand's competitive edge in the market. Given the nature of tasks associated with such roles, a high turnover rate in quick-service restaurants remains constant, particularly in highly developed countries offering lucrative career opportunities. Similar to other global enterprises, regardless of the organizational setup, quick-service restaurants encounter diverse issues that gauge team performance and management capability through key performance indices and adherence to core values. For instance, the Intellect Insights Journal (2023) has projected global Quick-Service Restaurant (QSR) market size was expected to reach USD 22,610 million by 2028, up from USD 14,190 million in 2022, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 6.8% during the forecast period. Lindner (2023) stated that the quick-service restaurant industry was a major employer in the United States, with 3.8 million people employed as of 2021. The top QSR player alone employed approximately 205,000 people worldwide and generated \$200 billion in revenue that same year. However, the industry also recorded an annual turnover rate in the US among selected quick-service restaurant workers ranging from 130% to 150%, reflecting instability within the sector. This scenario was attributed to various factors, including comparatively low wages, limited job security, and a lack of opportunities for career advancement. Given this situation, giant quick-service restaurants globally strategically employed job contractors.

Transitioning to the Philippines, a vibrant hub of culinary diversity, Balita (2023) stated that the convenience and speedy service provided by quick-service restaurant establishments made them the preferred choice for dining out or grabbing a meal on the go among Filipino consumers. With quick-service restaurant joints claiming more than half of the overall revenue, they amassed approximately 5.72 billion U.S. dollars in revenue in 2022 alone, registering a CAGR of 6.9% from 2019 to 2026. QSR giants in the Philippines also utilized job contracting services. This once-controversial practice was legally supported by the Labor Code of the Philippines, specifically in Articles 106 to 109, along with its most recent amendments outlined in DOLE Department Order 174, series of 2017.

In a report by Manila Standard Business (2024), Laguna emerged as the largest contributor to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), encompassing 5.0% in 2022. This significant economic growth triggered the expansion of diverse business establishments, including QSRs catered by job contractors across Laguna, offering a wide array of employment opportunities to its labor force. The presence of renowned brands in Laguna prompted consumers to set higher expectations, necessitating job contractors to deliver a requisite level of quality.

In the typical setting of a quick-service restaurant, ensuring smooth machinery operation, the availability of high-quality raw materials, and up-to-date meal preparation procedures were some critical imperatives. Equally crucial was the service crew's headcount completion and proficiency in operational aspects while strictly adhering to the company's standard operating procedures. The pool of full-time labor interested in QSR work was declining, posing productivity concerns for job contractors and threatening client operations. As an alternative, job contractors employed working students who often struggled with time management. Consequently, their job performance fell short and unintentionally violated the provisions of the service level agreement due to hybrid learning setups and inconsistent school schedules. Their divided attention led to a decline in proficiency and skills mastery.

This situation raised concerns among first-line managers regarding their ability to uphold the restaurant's brand promise to consumers, particularly when they lacked direct control over job contractor workers or agency crew. This challenge was compounded by the environmental responsibility of quick-service restaurants (QSRs) to the community by ensuring consistent compliance with government regulatory requirements. These productivity concerns highlighted the pressing need for a comprehensive study to evaluate the efficiency of job contractors and the productivity of selected QSRs in Laguna. The research aimed to provide valuable insights for QSR managers and policymakers to optimize operational efficiency, mitigate risks, and uphold service quality standards. Ultimately, the study sought to help safeguard the reputation and competitiveness of QSRs in the region.

Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

This research study was anchored on various theories to address the main problem of the research and to provide supporting details on job contracting efficiency and productivity by selected quick-service restaurants.

Firstly, the Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) of Ronald Coase (1937) and Oliver E. Williamson (1975) as cited in Tate and Ellram (2022). This theory highlighted that companies picked how to run a business based on what would cost them the least in transactions like maintenance expenses, quality control measure implementation, safety and security, labor costs, etc. Job contracting was a smart business move to cut down on these costs by letting companies hire outside help for certain jobs. They detailed that Transaction Cost Economics suggested that the choice between different governance structures depended on minimizing transaction costs, including costs related to

information, negotiation, and enforcement. Job contracting could be seen as a response to transaction costs, where firms contracted out certain tasks to external parties to minimize these costs.

Similarly, Nagle et al. (2020) specified that Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) theory provided insights into economic organization post-digital transformation. Digitization offered opportunities to explore TCE's boundaries and reaffirm its relevance for understanding firm organization and guiding policy. Hossain et al. (2021) specified that through TCE, it was discovered that Online Customer Reviews (OCR) facilitated the conversion of purchase intention into purchase behavior.

Secondly, the Resource Dependence Theory (RDT), introduced by Jeffrey Pfeffer and Gerald R. Salancik (1978, as cited in Panicker and Upadhyayula (2020)), demonstrated that organizations were heavily reliant on external entities for critical resources. These resources encompassed a broad spectrum, ranging from ingredients and supplies to customers and regulatory approvals. The theory emphasized that these dependencies significantly influenced organizational behavior and decision-making processes. Quick-service restaurants, like other organizations, actively managed relationships with external stakeholders to secure necessary resources and ensure operational sustainability. By strengthening strategic alliances, diversifying channels for resource acquisition, and adapting to changes in the environment, organizations optimized resources, enhanced their ability to cope with change, and maintained a competitive position in dynamic markets.

The theory underscored the importance of achieving a balance in power dynamics and mutual dependence between different entities in a supply chain. They noted that by leveraging RDT principles, job contractors strived for better information symmetry and mutual reliance with suppliers, ultimately enhancing stability and reducing uncertainty in relationships. Meanwhile, Malik and Hingley (2021) highlighted that this approach led to improved sustainability, especially during sales promotions, benefiting both contractors and suppliers in the quick-service restaurant sector. Additionally, Öztürk (2020) specified that RDT underscored the significance of understanding and managing connections with external stakeholders, which was crucial for job contractors navigating the complexities of the quick-service restaurant industry.

Thirdly, the Supplier Relationship Management (SRM), which originated from the works of Peter Kraljic in the late 1970s, emphasized the cultivation of collaborative and mutually beneficial partnerships with external suppliers and contractors. Quick-service restaurants adeptly employed SRM principles, influenced by Kraljic's seminal contributions, to judiciously select and manage job contractors. By embracing SRM, QSRs established a foundation of trust, transparency, and value creation that permeated the entirety of the relationship growth. This involved fostering open communication channels, negotiating fair terms, and aligning objectives with contractors to ensure mutual success.

Through the conscientious application of SRM practices, QSRs mitigated risks, capitalized on opportunities for innovation, and achieved sustainable competitive advantages in the dynamic market landscape. SRM played a crucial role in enhancing job contractor performance in the quick-service restaurant industry. Kashif and Al-Rawas (2022) noted that by implementing robust SRM practices, such as measuring supplier performance, analyzing data, and driving continuous improvement, quick-service restaurant businesses optimized supply chain efficiency and reduced risks of cost overruns. Additionally, Mukucha and Chari (2023) highlighted that strong collaboration with suppliers and customers through SRM practices significantly improved business performance, including financial health, market and sales performance, and operational efficiency. Therefore, effective SRM strategies were essential for enhancing job contractor performance in the quick-service restaurant sector.

The Agency Theory, developed by Michael C. Jensen and William H. Meckling in 1976, emphasized the need to align the interests of principals and agents to minimize agency costs and ensure optimal performance in contractual relationships. This alignment was achieved through mechanisms, such as well-structured contracts, performance-based incentives, and effective monitoring to mitigate risks of opportunistic behavior or shirking by agents.

Danivska and Appel-Meulenbroek (2021) highlighted that the theory encouraged collaboration between the principal (firm) and the agent (contractor) to harmonize their objectives. In the context of job contracting, the firm acted as the principal, while the contractor served as the agent. Ceylan et al. (2022) elaborated on the complexities of designing contracts and incentives that motivated contractors to act in the firm's best interests.

Yan and Hyman (2024) further extended the theory by exploring how social norms and cultural values influenced agent behavior, suggesting that agents could align with the principal's objectives beyond economic incentives. They also noted that the social bonds formed between principals and agents significantly shaped business decisions, fostering cooperation and mutual benefit. This broader perspective demonstrated how relational and cultural dimensions enhanced the efficiency and reliability of contractual relationships.

Various theories offered different perspectives on job contracting. While some emphasized fostering positive relationships between principals and job contractors through motivational approaches, others stressed the importance of considering the financial aspect when selecting job contractors to fulfil the brand promise, ultimately aiming to maximize profitability. Additionally, there was recognition of the value of relying on external experts for timely service delivery, particularly in urgent situations, as well as the benefits of engaging institutionalized job contractors with specialized expertise in specific areas.

The applicability of these theories spanned across different aspects of the quick-service restaurant industry, guiding management in making prudent business decisions.

Building on the theoretical framework outlined above, a conceptual framework was developed for this study as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1
Research Paradigm

This research study utilized the IV-DV research paradigm, where the independent variable was the level of efficiency among job contractors, focusing on the agency crew turnover rate, job satisfaction, and labor cost. The dependent variable was the productivity of selected quick-service restaurants, focusing on responsiveness, quality of work, and cost-effectiveness. In between the two variables was an arrow that showed that the level of job contractors' efficiency had a significant correlation and impact on the level of productivity of selected QSRs.

Research Questions

The primary objective of the study was to evaluate the efficiency of job contractors and the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants, which directly influenced the overall business performance. Specifically, the study aimed to address the following questions.

1. What is the level of efficiency among the job contractors in selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by their managers in Laguna in terms of:
 - 1.1. Turnover rate,
 - 1.2. Job satisfaction, and
 - 1.3. Labor cost?
2. What is the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by their managers in Laguna in terms of:
 - 2.1. Responsiveness,
 - 2.2. Quality of work, and
 - 2.3. Cost-effectiveness?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of efficiency among the job contractors and the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna?

4. Does the level of efficiency among the job contractors significantly impact the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed?

Hypotheses

In the context of this study, the following null hypotheses are tested for their significance:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between job contractors' efficiency level and the productivity level of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna.

Ho2: The efficiency level of job contractors does not significantly impact the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna.

Scope and Delimitation

This research study utilized a quantitative causal (regression) research design to determine the relationship and impact of job contractors' efficiency and the productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna.

Its primary objective was to examine the efficiency of job contractors catering to quick-service restaurants and their influence on the clients' business deliverables. The level of job contractors' efficiency consisted of agency crew turnover rate, job satisfaction, and labor cost. The study investigated the relationship among these three sub-variables to establish a foundation for understanding the efficiency of job contractors. On the other hand, the productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna focused on responsiveness, quality of work, and cost-effectiveness.

This study covered two quick-service restaurant brands, consisting of 27 branches operating in the province of Laguna and served by job contractors. The management teams, representing the principals of these brands, were chosen as the target respondents. The number of respondents was limited to 97 due to several factors and business decisions of the management.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter is dedicated to reviewing relevant literature that supports the core and methodology of the research. Published studies are analyzed with the research questions posed in defining the problem.

Job Contractors' Efficiency in Quick-Service Restaurants

Efficiency is the cornerstone of success in the quick-service restaurant (QSR) industry, directly influencing business sustainability, profitability, and overall stakeholder welfare. Regarding psychological and social stressors, Garlington et al. (2023) emphasized the detrimental impact of psychological and social stressors, such as racial code-switching, job insecurity, and role conflict, on employees' well-being and turnover intentions in the hospitality industry. They underscored how job stressors significantly

increased employees' desire to leave their roles, creating challenges for employers in retaining a stable workforce.

Similarly, Langove et al. (2022) reinforced this perspective by identifying job insecurity and role conflict as critical contributors to turnover intentions within QSRs, highlighting the intricate dynamics between workplace stressors and employee retention.

From a different perspective, regarding compensation and working conditions, Thusi and Chauke (2023) examined turnover from a broader perspective, focusing on the disparity between public and private sector compensation and working conditions. Their study revealed that inadequate workplace environments, lower pay, and limited growth opportunities contributed to prolonged vacancies and high turnover rates, suggesting that offering competitive salaries and improving workplace conditions could enhance retention.

Meanwhile, Xu et al. (2022) advanced the discussion by demonstrating the value of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in reducing turnover, emphasizing the importance of employee-related CSR initiatives. Their findings highlighted how improving employees' quality of work life and intrinsic motivation through CSR practices not only reduced turnover intentions but also strengthened employee loyalty and satisfaction.

Other important topic, such as training and development, human resource analytics, job positioning, and employee loyalty, also mattered in mitigating turnover rates. Albtosh et al. (2022) highlighted the interconnection of training satisfaction and employee loyalty, demonstrating how these factors indirectly reduced turnover intentions. Their research revealed that effective training programs and trainer efficacy positively impacted satisfaction levels, which in turn enhanced employee loyalty and reduced the likelihood of turnover.

Chakraborty et al. (2021) emphasized the role of human resource (HR) analytics in addressing turnover challenges. Chakraborty et al. detailed the financial and operational burdens of attrition, focusing on factors such as job position, overtime, and work levels as critical determinants of turnover rates.

Meanwhile, St. Aisyah Nur outlined how HR analytics frameworks, including descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, and prescriptive tools, enabled organizations to address specific concerns like career growth, compensation, and supportive work environments, fostering better retention outcomes.

Hence, implementing a program to mitigate turnover rates and improve work-life balance could have contributed positively to QSR operations. Salsabil and Cahyo (2023) provided practical solutions by advocating for compensation strategies tied to productivity outputs, ensuring fairness and adequacy for production workers. Their research identified salary as the most critical factor influencing retention, further supporting the need for competitive remuneration practices.

Bakar et al. (2022) extended this view by emphasizing the importance of work-life balance, particularly for women employees. They demonstrated how maintaining a balanced work-life environment enhanced job satisfaction, reduced turnover rates, and improved overall organizational performance.

Job satisfaction was a pivotal factor influencing employee retention and overall business performance in the quick-service restaurant industry. In terms of influences of work conditions, environment, and remuneration and compensation, Rajbanshi et al. (2022) emphasized that various factors such as working conditions, remuneration, relationships with supervisors, and interactions with co-workers significantly shaped job satisfaction. They found that remuneration and co-worker relationships were particularly influential, underlining the need for organizations to focus on these areas to improve employee contentment.

Similarly, Khoza (2022) echoed these sentiments, identifying poor working conditions and inefficiencies in human relations practices as major contributors to dissatisfaction, particularly when paired with limited career growth opportunities. They stressed the importance of creating a supportive and equitable work environment to combat these issues. To discuss the intrinsic and extrinsic influences, the study observed that intrinsic motivators like career growth enhanced satisfaction, while extrinsic factors like poor pay and restrictive policies contributed to dissatisfaction and increased turnover.

Moreover, Kapoor (2020) further highlighted the operational implications of labor inefficiencies, demonstrating that fair labor pricing and the provision of bonuses during high-demand periods effectively motivated employees, leading to enhanced productivity and satisfaction.

Furthermore, Saunders (2023) explored the impact of supervision quality, asserting that a lack of proper training resources for supervisors resulted in inconsistent management practices, reduced employee morale, and diminished job satisfaction, thus underscoring the critical need for evidence-based supervisory approaches.

In the perspective of stress and turnover intention, Wiastuti et al. (2023) explored the complex interplay between job stress, satisfaction, and turnover intentions, illustrating that job satisfaction served as a mediator that mitigated the adverse effects of stress on turnover. They noted that even in high-stress environments, employees with higher satisfaction levels exhibited lower turnover intentions.

In addition, Muda et al. (2022) expanded on this idea by linking job satisfaction to reduced absenteeism and turnover, as well as improved productivity, performance, and profitability. They advocated for fostering a supportive environment where employees feel valued, prioritizing health and safety measures, and implementing open communication channels to address employee concerns.

To elaborate more on the influences of performance and productivity levels on organizational outcomes, Imran and Wajid (2022) focused on the impact of emotional and behavioral factors, revealing that happiness, love of money, and work engagement

significantly enhanced employee performance, with job satisfaction acting as a mediator. However, they cautioned that role overload and empowerment did not directly influence performance outcomes, indicating the need for nuanced interventions.

In the concept of customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions, Ghosh et al. (2023) shifted focus to the customer-facing side of QSR operations, examining how service quality influences customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions. They discovered that positive employee attitudes and friendliness improved service outcomes, with satisfaction acting as a mediator between service quality and customer loyalty.

Moreover, another topic that needed to be discussed was retention and employee loyalty. Putra et al. (2023) broadened the perspective, identifying organizational factors such as effective leadership styles, justice, empowerment, and emotional intelligence as critical to job satisfaction and retention. They warned against toxic leadership and job stress, which significantly undermined employee satisfaction and organizational commitment.

Efficient labor cost management and cost control are paramount in today's highly competitive business environment. A critical approach to labor efficiency involves improving how labor is organized and regulated. Shalmieva et al. (2022) highlighted the significance of creating high-efficiency jobs by analyzing various factors influencing labor organization, regulation, and costs. They pointed out that technical, organizational, psychophysiological, social, and economic factors play crucial roles in shaping labor dynamics. The study emphasized the growing impact of economic digitalization on labor practices, which necessitated adjusting work norms to adapt to changing socio-economic conditions. This adaptability ensured that businesses could optimize their workforce management in a digital era.

To support this, Kuchina and Havrys (2022) also focused on refining labor systems, specifically labor rationing concepts. They proposed enhancing time and production norms to better fit modern production conditions, advocating for more effective labor management practices. By aligning labor regulations with contemporary needs, businesses could foster greater productivity and operational efficiency, reducing waste and optimizing performance.

Similarly, Mzughulga and Moiseeva (2023) addressed methods for improving efficiency within competitive business environments. They recommended the adoption of direct labor cost monitoring, such as implementing piece-rate wages, to encourage improved performance and reduce inefficiencies. Furthermore, their study emphasized identifying opportunities to increase production capacity, which could help businesses lower unit production costs and boost overall efficiency.

Technology plays a crucial role in improving operational efficiency across industries. Xu et al. (2022) suggested a shift from traditional maintenance practices to more efficient and high-quality operation systems, particularly for businesses in sectors like smart courts. This model focused on the continuous operation and maintenance of

information systems, which ensured optimal performance while reducing downtime and operational inefficiencies. The integration of such technologies into business practices significantly improved labor efficiency, enhanced decision-making, and ultimately reduced costs across the board.

To discuss the concept, innovative business models such as dark kitchens and the use of freelance labor gained traction as methods for reducing operational costs. Marinakou et al. (2023) discussed the rise of dark kitchens as a popular business model, particularly in the food service industry, due to their ability to significantly cut operational costs and improve productivity. However, they also raised concerns about worker exploitation within these kitchens due to poor working conditions and unfair contractual agreements. To maintain a sustainable reputation and reduce high employee turnover, their study stressed the need for businesses to implement fair labor practices in these models.

Similarly, Лобашев et al. (2020) explored the cost benefits of employing freelance labor. By hiring freelancers for specific tasks, businesses reduced overall operational costs, as they only paid for tasks completed rather than committing to long-term employment contracts. Freelancers also tended to be more focused on completing tasks efficiently, which further reduced operational expenses. This model not only lowered labor costs but also enhanced business flexibility, allowing companies to scale their workforce based on fluctuating demands.

Strategic decision-making was another critical component of optimizing labor and resource management. Olatunji et al. (2022) examined the factors influencing the success of proposal decisions in construction and project management. They identified key elements such as administrative depth, strategic direction, market advantage, and openness to new technologies as crucial for successful project outcomes. Their study emphasized that well-planned and rational proposal decisions, aligned with risk management strategies, significantly impacted a project's success and reduced associated costs.

In industries such as quick-service restaurants, managing customer queues efficiently improves operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. Ghazali and Amit (2022) analyzed different queue management models and found that the single-line with multi-server model (M/M/2) outperformed the multi-line model (2*M/M/1). The implementation of the more efficient model resulted in reduced service time, shorter queues, and less idle time, ultimately contributing to lower operational costs and better customer experiences. Efficient queue management directly influenced profitability by improving service delivery and minimizing delays.

The application of Lean management principles in service industries, including in QSR, was another avenue for improving operational efficiency. Kocerova et al. (2023) explored the integration of Lean and quality work within the context of digitalization and industrial revolutions 4.0 and 5.0. They stressed the importance of adapting Lean practices to modern digital realities, as traditional Lean approaches were not as effective

in today's rapidly evolving business landscape. By using Lean metrics and visualizing quality outcomes, businesses streamlined their operations, reduced waste, and improved service quality, all of which contributed to cost reduction and enhanced efficiency.

Productivity Level of Quick-Service Restaurants

Quick-service restaurants often face significant financial and productivity concerns, as illustrated by Del Valle et al. (2022), who examined how restaurant businesses navigated the unexpected difficulties posed by pandemics. Their study showed that pandemic-related expenses, such as new supplies and employee training, led to a drastic reduction in income, forcing businesses to adapt by reducing staff and modifying operations. This highlighted the broader operational and financial constraints that affected QSRs, such as budget allocation and menu adjustments, which were critical factors for business owners to manage during challenging times.

Another common issue included food safety and contamination. Food safety and contamination risks were also key concerns for QSRs. Sahoo et al. (2022) pointed out that food was a primary vehicle for zoonotic pathogens, which could lead to global outbreaks. They advocated for advanced food processing and preservation techniques to mitigate contamination risks, which were crucial for maintaining food safety in QSRs.

Similarly, Holah (2023) further emphasized the necessity of managing contamination risks when contractors were involved in tasks like equipment installation, underscoring the importance of strict safety protocols.

To deal with the context of time, responsiveness in operations played a critical role in the efficiency and success of QSRs. Ricardo (2022) explored the relationship between responsiveness, efficiency, and accountability in corporate governance, establishing the importance of these factors in restaurant operations. This responsiveness directly impacted service speed and accuracy.

Likewise, Morinaga et al. (2022) found that responsiveness in endovascular treatments could be compared to the responsiveness needed in QSR operations, where delays or discrepancies led to customer dissatisfaction.

In addition, Raghuram and Saleeshya (2021) supported this by demonstrating that improving responsiveness in supply chains could enhance customer service, operational efficiency, and overall profitability, which was equally applicable to QSRs.

Moreover, the utilization of technology significantly enhanced the responsiveness of contractors in QSRs, although there were barriers to overcome. Liashenko et al. (2022) discussed the productivity concerns QSRs faced in fostering a data-driven culture, such as lack of government engagement and financial support. Overcoming these obstacles was essential for ensuring the long-term success of technology-driven strategies that improved contractor responsiveness.

Furthermore, Altaş (2022) echoed this by highlighting the accelerated adoption of technology in QSR operations, such as social distance tracking systems and drones for

delivery, which helped improve efficiency and service quality, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

To discuss further the topic of responsiveness, contractor performance was influenced by the resilience of the supply chain. Mukucha and Chari (2023) emphasized the importance of strategies like velocity, versatility, and visibility in strengthening QSR supply chains, noting that production contracts reduced vulnerabilities while marketing contracts enhanced capabilities. These strategies were essential for navigating disruptions and ensuring smooth operations.

Sandoval et al. (2020) and Indrawati et al. (2020) further emphasized the need for lean approaches and digital technologies to optimize resource utilization and improve service system performance, ensuring contractor efficiency in QSRs.

Finally, Lee et al. (2022) introduced the potential of crowd-sourcing food delivery, which highlighted the role of technology in enhancing job performance and worker retention in QSRs. Their research found that while crowd-sourcing could reduce job commitment and performance, social systems such as networks, trust, and shared vision could mitigate these risks, emphasizing the balance between technology and social factors for optimal performance in QSR delivery systems. This underscored the importance of addressing both technological and human factors in improving overall operational outcomes.

Another important topic discussed concerning QSR operations was the variation in the quality of work delivered by job contractors in the quick-service restaurant (QSR) industry, influenced by several interrelated factors, both internal and external to the organization. Ubaidillah and Parlinda (2023) identified key elements such as job training, work motivation, work environment, and role overload as critical factors that significantly affected employee productivity, which in turn impacted the quality of work. Alongside these, work engagement and happiness also played a vital role in ensuring high-quality service delivery. Furthermore, empowerment and work-life balance were crucial in boosting job contractor performance and productivity.

Additionally, the gig economy, as explored by Shin et al. (2023), shed light on how high employee turnover and customer dissatisfaction in industries like ridesharing negatively affected service quality. This connection underscored the importance of stable employment conditions for contractors in maintaining consistent service quality within QSRs.

Transitioning from internal factors affecting job contractors to external elements that influenced service quality, Neacșu and Tulbure (2023) highlighted the rising demand for healthier and more sustainable food choices as a driving force behind new strategies in the QSR industry. These changes were designed to improve operational efficiency while appealing to health-conscious consumers, thus enhancing overall service quality.

Similarly, Etuk et al. (2022) emphasized the significance of service tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy in shaping consumer preferences in

QSRs. Their findings suggested that the work performed by job contractors, especially in terms of customer interaction, directly influenced consumer perceptions.

To support this, Salles et al. (2022) further validated this by identifying service quality gaps in QSRs, particularly in areas such as reliability and tangibility. Their study pointed out the need for improvements in aspects like order delivery, cleanliness, and supply efficiency to better meet customer expectations and enhance satisfaction.

The convergence of internal and external factors highlighted the critical role of technology in shaping service quality. Udayalakshmi and Sridevi (2023) examined how disruptive technologies like artificial intelligence, big data, robotics, and automation transformed service delivery models within QSRs. These technologies were essential in adapting service quality frameworks to meet modern consumer expectations.

Furthermore, the impact of external concerns, such as the COVID-19 pandemic on supply chains in unrelated industries, as discussed by Farooq et al. (2022), demonstrated the need for resilience and effective management strategies to maintain service quality during disruptions. Together, these internal and external factors emphasized the importance of a holistic approach to improving work quality in QSRs, integrating contractor performance with broader industry trends and technological advancements.

The utilization of job contractors in quick service significantly influenced cost-effectiveness and profitability. Oleah et al. (2022) identified critical barriers such as payment delays, faulty work, incomplete designs, and inflation, which hindered a contractor's ability to deliver on time and within budget. These issues, along with high wages and inefficient bidding strategies, affected the financial performance of QSRs relying on contractors.

Similarly, Vishwakarma et al. (2022) further elaborated on the influence of labor productivity factors such as crew composition, design complexity, and expertise in determining contractor efficiency, ultimately impacting the profitability and competitiveness of QSR businesses. These findings suggested that effective contractor management and strategic interventions were key to enhancing contractor profitability and, by extension, the success of QSR operations.

Dealing with the financial condition of the QSR as a business, Martin et al. (2021) explored staffing strategies, comparing contractor labor versus direct employee hires in dynamic demand environments. The study emphasized that contractors, when compensated with dynamic wages, could offer flexibility and profit-bound advantages, making them a valuable resource for QSRs experiencing fluctuating demand.

On the other hand, Binik-Thomas (2022) examined the risks of contractor engagement without clear contracts. Highlighting the importance of financial diligence and clear communication, the study cautioned against starting work without securing written agreements, which could lead to payment delays, disapproval, and unforeseen costs. The findings emphasized the necessity of establishing transparent expectations, pre-

approved protocols, and clear authority within QSR teams to effectively manage contractors and avoid operational risks.

The role of outsourcing, particularly in the context of IT services, also played a significant role in QSR operations. Research by Qureshi et al. (2023) confirmed that the adoption of IT played a crucial role in achieving supply chain agility, which in turn helped reduce costs and improve the operational performance of firms. The study model offered a valuable framework for examining the impact of IT adoption on supply chain agility and its subsequent outcomes.

In relation to that, Toku and Takyi (2020) examined IT outsourcing's impact on QSRs, utilizing Transaction Cost Economics (TCE) and Resource-Based View (RBV) frameworks. Their studies found that outsourcing IT functions could streamline operations and reduce costs by allowing QSRs to focus on core activities while leveraging external expertise. However, the study cautioned that outsourcing did not come without challenges. Post-contractual issues and potential operational inefficiencies could arise if not carefully managed. The need for due diligence and appropriate safeguards to mitigate these risks was essential for the successful integration of outsourcing in QSR operations.

The QSR industry contributed unfavorably to the environment and the community. Sustainability was another critical factor influencing QSR operations, particularly concerning food waste management. Sobhy et al. (2020) addressed the importance of reducing food waste in the food service industry, which had significant managerial and economic implications. Their research found that waste levels tended to be higher in low-volume restaurants, highlighting the need for tailored waste management strategies to improve sustainability and operational efficiency. By implementing targeted practices, such as better inventory management and waste reduction protocols, QSRs could enhance both sustainability and cost-effectiveness, while contributing positively to the environment. This tied into the broader discussion on operational efficiency and the growing emphasis on responsible practices in the food service sector.

To discuss further options to gain more profit, Pasha and Williams (2022) examined the effectiveness of outsourcing in QSR operations, questioning the commonly held belief that outsourcing always enhances performance. Their study found that outsourcing did not always improve efficiency or cost-effectiveness in QSRs and, in some cases, compromised service quality and customer satisfaction.

This study added an important layer to the conversation by underscoring the need for QSRs to carefully assess the potential trade-offs between cost savings and service quality when outsourcing decisions. Balancing these factors was essential for maintaining operational efficiency and sustaining long-term success in the highly competitive QSR industry.

Job Contractor Efficiency and Productivity of Quick-Service Restaurants

The efficiency and performance of employees were crucial to the success of quick-service restaurants. Madhavi and Mehrotra (2020) emphasized that the trust and

competence of employees significantly affected organizational success. Competence management, which involved building employee confidence through training and skill updates, was essential for business growth.

Furthermore, Rodrigo et al. (2022) underlined the importance of job satisfaction in improving employee performance. They found a positive correlation between job satisfaction and performance, emphasizing salary equity, supportive supervisor relationships, and training as key factors.

Similarly, Chico et al. (2023) explored how organizational culture impacted employee performance, showing that cultural aspects like involvement, adaptability, and consistency positively influenced job satisfaction, which directly reflected in business performance. Both studies highlighted how improving employee satisfaction could drive higher productivity and better service quality, making employee satisfaction a central factor in organizational performance.

The issue of employee turnover was closely linked to the factors that influenced employee satisfaction and performance. Moodley (2023) revealed that high employee turnover negatively affected organizational performance. High turnover rates were often associated with dissatisfaction with remuneration, and the study suggested that talent management programs and change management efforts could help address these concerns.

Vasantham and Aithal (2022), along with Naru and Rehman (2020), identified key causes of turnover, including job stress, low satisfaction, and inadequate wages. Their findings suggested that addressing these issues could help retain employees, thus improving productivity and organizational sustainability.

Moreover, Qin et al. (2022) discussed the detrimental effects of high employee turnover on firm performance, particularly in small firms and tight labor markets. The higher the turnover, the lower the financial performance, making turnover management an essential element in maintaining competitive advantage.

In the QSR industry, the quality of service provided to customers was another critical factor that directly impacted business performance. Truong and Nguyen (2023) examined how service quality affected customer satisfaction, particularly among Generation Y customers. Their research highlighted the importance of attributes such as empathy, assurance, and reliability in shaping customer perceptions. These elements not only boosted customer satisfaction but also enhanced customer loyalty, which was vital for sustaining business growth in a competitive market. This focus on customer satisfaction was closely connected to the broader theme of operational efficiency and cost management, as maintaining high service quality could directly affect operational costs and profitability.

Operational efficiency was a significant determinant of QSR's success, and managing costs effectively was essential to sustaining profitability. Kartika and Oktarini (2022) found that operational costs had a strong influence on labor productivity. They

suggested that investing in human capital and efficient managerial practices could optimize productivity while keeping costs manageable.

This connection between labor productivity and cost management aligned with the findings of Lobel et al. (2021), who discussed the flexibility of contractor models in managing operational efficiency. Contractors, unlike employees, were more adaptable, particularly in uncertain demand situations, and could help reduce operational costs.

Marks and Golovey (2020) further supported this by showing that contractors, particularly in franchisee-owned outlets, tended to outperform corporate-owned QSRs due to increased flexibility and entrepreneurial motivation. This led to a more efficient use of resources and enhanced business performance during peak times, reinforcing the idea that contractors could contribute significantly to operational efficiency.

Lastly, the selection and management of contractors in QSRs played a pivotal role in operational success. Ravari et al. (2020) highlighted the importance of considering factors like technical capabilities, previous experience, and timely payment when selecting contractors for projects. These factors ensured the successful completion of tasks and contributed to the overall efficiency of the operation.

Similarly, Gündüz and Al-Ajji (2021) further discussed the influence of contractor decisions on project outcomes, with considerations such as workload and employer reputation being critical to maintaining project quality and efficiency. These studies underscored the impact of contractor management on operational performance, showing that effective contractor relationships were key to achieving high efficiency and reducing costs, thus supporting business sustainability.

Synthesis

Factors influencing employee turnover and strategies to mitigate it in the quick-service restaurant (QSR) industry emphasized the role of efficiency as a critical success factor. In QSRs, business sustainability and profitability were closely tied to efficiency, which encompassed turnover rates, job satisfaction, and labor costs. These factors significantly affected organizational success and decision-making. Regarding the different factors influencing turnover rate, the study conducted by Garlington et al. (2023), Thusi and Chauke (2023), Langove et al. (2022), and Alboosh et al. (2022) identified psychological social stressors, job insecurity, and role conflict as factors that negatively influenced turnover intentions. On the other hand, Xu et al. (2022) and Chakraborty et al. (2021) reported that better compensation, favorable working conditions, high quality of work life, intrinsic motivation, training satisfaction, job position, and work level were key factors that positively influenced employee retention and loyalty. Additionally, Salsabil and Cahyo (2023), Bakar et al. (2022), and St. Aisyah Nur (2022) highlighted that competitive remuneration enhanced the level of productivity, work-life balance improved job satisfaction and performance, and human resource analytics facilitated the development of tailored interventions to promote career growth and create supportive work environments.

The studies by Rajbanshi et al. (2022), Khoza (2022), Kapoor (2020), and Saunders (2023) enumerated various factors negatively influencing job satisfaction, including poor working conditions, inadequate supervisor relationships, lack of career advancement opportunities, intrinsic and extrinsic concerns, labor pricing inefficiencies, absence of bonuses, and insufficient supervisor training. In contrast, Putra et al. (2023) highlighted the positive effects of leadership styles, organizational justice, rewards, and employee empowerment. Similarly, Wiastuti et al. (2023) identified job satisfaction as a mediator between stress and turnover intentions, while Muda et al. (2022) linked higher job satisfaction to reduced turnover, lower absenteeism, and improved organizational performance. Imran and Wajid (2022) emphasized the positive impact of happiness, love of money, and work engagement on employee performance, and Ghosh et al. (2023) explored how service quality and employee attitudes influence customer satisfaction and loyalty.

To enhance job satisfaction, researchers such as Muda et al. (2022), Saunders (2023), Kapoor (2020), Salsabil and Cahyo (2023), Putra et al. (2023), and Khoza (2022) recommended fostering a supportive work environment, improving supervisory training, implementing fair labor pricing and competitive bonuses, promoting effective leadership styles, developing emotional intelligence within teams, and addressing inefficiencies in HR practices.

In terms of labor cost, studies by Shalmieva et al. (2022), Kuchina and Havrys (2022), Mzughulga and Moiseeva (2023), Xu et al. (2022), Marinakou et al. (2023), Лобашев et al. (2020), Olatunji et al. (2022), Ghazali and Amit (2022), and Kocerova et al. (2023) discussed various strategies and factors influencing cost management. These included high-efficiency jobs, psychophysiological aspects, economic digitalization in labor practices, refining labor organization and regulation systems, piece-rate wages for direct labor cost monitoring, efficient operation and maintenance of information systems, cost-reduction strategies with fair working conditions, the use of freelance labor for flexibility and cost savings, proposal decisions and strategic alignment, queue management efficiency, and Lean management challenges with digital adaptations in service industries. These aspects directly impacted cost management across different business industries, including quick-service restaurants.

Given the different financial concerns related to productivity in QSRs, Del Valle et al. (2022) and Sahoo et al. (2022) discussed the financial strain caused by unexpected events like the pandemic and food safety concerns, including risks of foodborne zoonoses from QSR service providers. Amidst these concerns regarding productivity, responsiveness plays a crucial role. Mukucha and Chari (2023), Altaş (2022), Lee et al. (2022), Ricardo (2022), Liashenko et al. (2022), Raghuram and Saleeshya (2021), and Sandoval et al. (2020) focused on operational efficiency, barriers to technology adoption, the role of drones and social distancing systems, improving supply chain resilience and contractor performance/responsiveness, and the impact of crowd-sourcing in food delivery on service speed and customer satisfaction, all contributing to operational effectiveness. These studies illustrated the interconnectedness of financial, operational,

and technological factors in addressing the QSRs' productivity concerns and improving overall performance.

Discussing the quality of work influenced by job contractor services, Ubaidillah and Parlinda (2023) and Shin et al. (2023) emphasized the importance of a positive work environment, work engagement, work-life balance, and the impact of the gig economy. On the other hand, customer expectations also play a key role in shaping work quality. Neacșu and Tulbure (2023), Etuk et al. (2022), Salles et al. (2022), and Udayalakshmi and Sridevi (2023) highlighted that consumer expectations for healthier options, service quality (responsiveness), tangibility, reliability, and technological advancements like AI utilization are critical factors in enhancing job contractor performance and service delivery. Neglecting these factors can lead to high turnover rates and customer dissatisfaction. From a broader perspective, Farooq et al. (2022) discussed the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on supply chains and the importance of service quality management.

In terms of profitability, several studies explored factors affecting contractor performance and profitability in quick-service restaurants. Oleah et al. (2022), Vishwakarma et al. (2022), Binik-Thomas (2022), Martin et al. (2021), Pasha and Williams (2022), Qureshi et al. (2023), and Sobhy et al. (2020) highlighted various productivity concerns such as payment delays, faulty work, design complexity, high labor costs, signed contracts, and pre-approved scope adjustments, flexibility in adjusting contractor wages, the drawbacks of outsourcing, and the need for careful evaluation. Furthermore, they addressed sustainability concerns in QSRs, particularly waste reduction, and suggested waste management strategies. Collectively, these studies underscored the interconnectedness of contractor management, outsourcing, and sustainability in enhancing profitability and operational efficiency in QSRs.

In dealing with employee performance and satisfaction, Madhavi and Mehrotra (2020), Rodrigo et al. (2022), Chico et al. (2023), Vasantham and Aithal (2022), Naru and Rehman (2020), Moodley (2023), and Qin et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of competence and skill management for business success, the positive relationship between job satisfaction and employee performance, factors like salary equity and supportive supervision, organizational culture, including involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission, factors affecting employee turnover and retention, such as job stress, satisfaction, and motivation, the negative impact of high turnover on organizational performance, particularly in small firms, and stressed the need for talent management.

From the perspective of service quality impact on business performance, Truong and Nguyen (2023), Adelia and Aprianingsih (2023), Truong and Nguyen (2023) and Adelia and Aprianingsih (2023) demonstrated how service quality, customer satisfaction, and marketing strategies contribute to customer loyalty and business competitiveness. In terms of operational efficiency and cost management, Kartika and Oktarini (2022), Lobel et al. (2021), Marks and Golovey (2020), Gündüz and Al-Ajji (2021), and Ravari et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of investing in human capital and managerial

resources, the flexibility of contractors in handling uncertain demand, higher motivation and flexibility, and the key factors in contractor selection, such as workload, experience, and timely payment, which influence project outcomes and efficiency. These studies highlight the interconnected factors driving employee performance, operational success, and effective contractor management in the QSR industry.

Upon thorough review of the related studies and literature, the predominant focus has been on optimizing the performance of job contractors within quick-service restaurants. However, despite providing a comprehensive discussion about the productivity level of QSRs and emphasizing the importance of job contractors' efficiency, particularly in responsiveness, quality of work, and cost-effectiveness, various studies have revealed significant research gaps.

In terms of job contractors' efficiency, while many studies focus on employee productivity and satisfaction, there was a conceptual gap in understanding how job contractors' efficiency and operational setup impacted QSR operations. Additionally, there was a methodological gap, as research lacked specific methods for effectively managing job contractors.

The practical and policy gaps concerning contractor responsiveness in quick-service restaurants were also observed. While existing research underscored responsiveness as crucial for corporate governance, efficiency, and profitability, there was a notable absence of practical methods tailored to measure and enhance contractor responsiveness within QSR operations. Furthermore, a conceptual gap existed in determining the contribution of job contractors to the operational success of QSR operations.

Regarding the quality of work, an empirical gap was identified. Various studies determined critical factors like training, motivation, and work environment for improving work productivity in QSRs. However, there was a gap in the practical testing of comprehensive job contractor management programs in diverse QSR settings to determine their applicability and effectiveness.

On cost-effectiveness, a temporal gap existed due to insufficient studies on recent developments, particularly the use of job contractors in QSR operations in Laguna. Additionally, there was a contextual gap as no study had yet been conducted on job contractors catering to QSRs in Laguna.

Furthermore, a practical and policy gap was evident. Although factors affecting profitability and labor productivity were discussed, detailed strategies and holistic approaches for effectively addressing these productivity concerns in QSR operations were lacking.

This study was able to bridge the identified gaps by focusing on several key areas: improving contractor responsiveness, enhancing work quality, and achieving greater cost-effectiveness in QSR operations. By addressing these critical issues, the research

developed a comprehensive strategy for optimizing performance and efficiency in the industry.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative research approach, specifically adopting a quantitative causal (regression) research design. Descriptive research offered a portrait of the present situation, capturing it as it stood. Correlational research unveiled connections between variables and forecasted future occurrences based on existing understanding.

Correlation research, as described by Bhandari (2023), analyzed relationships without manipulating variables, focusing on existing conditions and using correlation coefficients to measure the strength and direction of associations.

A descriptive-causal research design was employed to determine the extent of the relationship between the level of job efficiency and the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna. This involved gathering data to test hypotheses.

Research Locale

The research locale denoted the specific area and scope of the study. The data used in this research originated from selected quick-service restaurants employing job contractors for tasks that may impact the productivity level of selected quick-service restaurants. Those selected Quick-service restaurants were specifically those operating in the selected cities and municipalities in Laguna such as Siniloan, Sta Cruz, Bay, Los Banos, San Pablo City, Calamba City, Cabuyao City, Santa Rosa City, Biñan City, San Pedro City.

Population and Sampling

The population for this study consisted of managers from selected quick-service restaurants, serving as the principal's representatives and clients of job contractors. The selection of respondents followed an incidental sampling method, wherein the Human Resources department assisted the researcher by distributing the survey questionnaires to the target-identified respondents, inconveniencing them with the time but ensuring representation from each branch. To determine the appropriate sample size, G*Power 3.1.9.7 software was utilized, with an effect size of 0.361 and a statistical power of 95%.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents for this study were managers of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna that employed job contractors. These managers were selected due to their extensive knowledge and expertise in the operational aspects of running a QSR, which is directly relevant to the study's subject matter.

The total population was approximately 125 managers, from which a sample size of 97 was pre-identified to ensure representation from each QSR branch in Laguna. Survey questionnaires were distributed electronically, achieving a response rate of 76.28%, with 74 respondents completing the survey.

Research Instrument

The study utilized researcher-made questionnaires as its primary instrument, crafted following a thorough review of pertinent literature on job contractor efficiency and productivity of quick-service restaurants. This literature review played a pivotal role in shaping the formulation of questionnaire items. The questionnaires comprised two distinct parts, each tailored to address different aspects of the research inquiry. Part I was dedicated to assessing the level of efficiency among the job contractors in selected quick-service restaurants, while Part II focused on evaluating the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants. To gather responses, respondents utilized 4-point Likert scales, assigning numerical scores to indicate their level of satisfaction towards each statement provided within the questionnaires as shown in the table below:

Rating scale of level of efficiency among the job contractors in selected quick-service restaurants

Rating	Range	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Efficient
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree	Efficient
2	1.76 - 2.50	Disagree	Slightly Efficient
1	1.00 - 1.75	Strongly Disagree	Inefficient

Rating scale of productivity level of selected quick-service restaurants

Rating	Range	Categorical Response	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Productive
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree	Productive
2	1.76 - 2.50	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Productive
1	1.00 - 1.75	Disagree	Not Productive

Validation of the Instrument

The initial draft of the questionnaires was presented to the thesis adviser for analysis and feedback. To ensure technical accuracy and relevance to the topic, professionals in the field of study were consulted. The validators included the appointed statistician, the school's research director, and a professor from Laguna College of Business and Arts with expertise in validating research instruments. Additionally, two external validators were consulted: a certified public accountant and area manager in the QSR industry, and an academican who completed a doctoral program in business

administration at San Pablo College. The specific suggestions and comments provided by these validators were carefully incorporated into the final revisions of the questionnaires.

Based on Lawshe's Content Validity Index (CVI) calculation, it was concluded that all panelists agreed, indicating that the questionnaire scale had achieved a satisfactory level of content validity. All the questions were deemed essential, resulting in a CVR of 1.00. To further validate the instrument, a pilot test was conducted with thirty individuals who served as dry-run respondents. The researcher-made questionnaire passed the Cronbach's Alpha reliability test, yielding Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of 0.943 for job contractors' efficiency and 0.964 for QSRs' productivity. These results demonstrated the instrument's reliability for both constructs.

Data-Gathering Procedure

Upon approval of the research proposal and validation of the research instrument, a letter of request and the questionnaires were sent to the HR department of the QSR companies to obtain consent for conducting a study on the efficiency of job contractors concerning the QSRs' level of productivity daily. After receiving the approval, a relevant survey was then conducted. The researcher-made questionnaires were then electronically distributed and collected, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted. In addition, a statistician was consulted for data processing and interpretation.

Treatment of Quantitative Data

1. This study applied the following statistical treatments using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS):
2. The mean and a four-point Likert Scale were utilized to depict the efficiency level among the job contractors and the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna.
3. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to determine the relationship between the efficiency of job contractors and the level of productivity of selected QSR in Laguna.
4. Regression analysis was used to evaluate the impact of the efficiency level among job contractors on the productivity level of selected quick-service restaurants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the level of efficiency among the job contractors in selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by its managers in Laguna in terms of Turnover rate?

The job contractors in selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by their managers in Laguna in terms of Turnover rate were Efficient (3.05). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Efficient. Furthermore, the indicator "Skilled agency crew feel like they intend to remain in their positions" had the highest computed mean of 3.22

meanwhile, the indicator “The agency crew show a sign of loyalty towards the QSR” had the lowest computed mean of 2.85.

1.1 Turnover Rate

Table 1.1

Level of Job Contractors’ Efficiency in Selected Quick-Service Restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Turnover Rate

Indicators in terms of Turnover rate	(\bar{X}) Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1 Most of the agency crews aspire to long-term positions.	2.96	Efficient	7.5
2 The level of mastery among agency crew resembles the stability of operations in the QSR.	3.12	Efficient	4
3 Skilled agency crew feel like they intend to remain in their positions.	3.22	Efficient	1
4 The agency crew training plan for newly deployed members is effective.	3.11	Efficient	5
5 The job contractor is implementing agency crew recognition programs within the QSR.	3.20	Efficient	2
6 The agency crew engagement mirrors the team morale in the QSR.	3.16	Efficient	3
7 The phasing of agency crew deployment is reasonable.	3.00	Efficient	6
8 Agency crew commitment influences the quality of service provided by the QSR as a business.	2.96	Efficient	7.5
9 The agency crew showed a sign of loyalty towards the QSR.	2.85	Efficient	10
10 The agency crew manifest an interest in pursuing careers within the QSR.	2.95	Efficient	9
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.05	Efficient	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree / Highly Efficient 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree / Slightly Efficient
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree / Efficient 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree / Not Efficient

This implies that job contractors efficiently manage turnover rates, which is crucial for maintaining smooth operations in the QSR industry. Moreover, they demonstrate success in retaining skilled personnel, as evidenced by the great number of skilled job contractor members, who work for their assigned QSRs for an extended period. This indicates that these workers appreciate the work environment and the camaraderie they share with their colleagues. However, the findings also reveal an opportunity for improvement in fostering loyalty among agency crew members with the QSR assignment. Strengthening this aspect is essential to securing their commitment and ensuring alignment with the organizational goals of the QSRs.

In line with the findings, Thusi and Chauke (2023) observed that employees were more likely to remain in their roles when provided with better pay and favorable working conditions. Similarly, Salsabil and Cahyo (2023) emphasized that salary was the most

critical factor influencing employees' decision to stay. Regarding employee loyalty, Albitoosh et al. (2022) linked training satisfaction to increased loyalty and reduced turnover, noting that its influence on turnover intentions was mediated through loyalty.

1.2 Job Satisfaction

Table 1.2

Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency in Selected Quick-Service Restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Job Satisfaction

Indicators in terms of Job satisfaction	(\bar{X}) Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The agency crew is satisfied with their current working condition.	3.23	Efficient	3
2. The remuneration received by agency crew members in relation to their job responsibilities is satisfactory.	3.14	Efficient	9
3. The agency crew members appear to enjoy having good working relationships with the managers in the QSR.	3.15	Efficient	6
4. The agency crew members experience a sense of camaraderie with their co-workers in the QSR.	3.24	Efficient	2
5. The agency crew members acknowledge the stability offered by their positions in terms of job security.	3.36	Highly Efficient	1
6. The agency crew members handle job stress as part of their responsibilities in their current roles.	3.14	Efficient	9
7. The agency crew members have work-life balance in their jobs.	3.15	Efficient	6
8. The agency crew members receive recognition or bonuses for their performance.	3.14	Efficient	9
9. The overall organizational culture is acceptable to agency crew members.	3.15	Efficient	6
10. The agency crew shows signs of satisfaction with the opportunities for career growth within the QSR.	3.16	Efficient	4
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.19	Efficient	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Efficient	1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Efficient		
2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Efficient	1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Efficient		

The job contractors in selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by its managers in Laguna in terms of Job Satisfaction were Efficient (3.19). Majority of indicators were verbally interpreted as Efficient. Furthermore, the indicator “The agency crew members acknowledge the stability offered by their positions in terms of job security.” had the highest computed mean of 3.36 or Highly Efficient meanwhile, the indicators “The remuneration received by agency crew members in relation to their job

responsibilities is satisfactory.”, “The agency crew members handle job stress as part of their responsibilities in their current roles.”, and “The agency crew members receive recognition or bonuses for their performance.” had the lowest computed mean of 3.14.

The findings suggest that job stability is a key strength of the system, positively contributing to the agency crew's overall satisfaction and sense of security. Additionally, fostering a strong working relationship enhances open communication within the workplace. Considering the current inflation, job security assures that the job contractor members can support their families and meet personal needs, regardless of their role within the organization.

Although the overall ratings are generally positive, lower scores in remuneration, stress management, and recognition for performance indicate dissatisfaction among agency crew members. Insufficient remuneration directly reduces work performance and productivity by lowering motivation and output. Job stress challenges crew members in managing their roles, leading to frustration that affects their performance and increases turnover intentions. Furthermore, a lack of recognition for their contributions lowers morale and motivation, which ultimately impacts job satisfaction. Addressing these issues improves job satisfaction.

Langove et al. (2022) asserted that job security and minimized role conflict were pivotal for enhancing job satisfaction within the restaurant industry. Muda et al. (2022) echoed this sentiment, emphasizing the significant role of supportive work environments in fostering camaraderie among colleagues. According to their findings, a cohesive and friendly atmosphere not only boosted morale but also led to tangible benefits, such as decreased absenteeism. They argued that when employees felt secure in their roles and had strong, supportive relationships with their co-workers, their overall job satisfaction improved, and they were more likely to be present and engaged in their work. This underscored the importance of creating and maintaining a workplace culture that prioritized both job stability and interpersonal connections, as these factors collectively contributed to a more productive and satisfied workforce.

Many studies demonstrated that fair remuneration, wage transparency, salary equity, and supportive supervisory relationships were essential in enhancing job satisfaction and motivation, which ultimately led to higher-quality service delivery. Moodley (2023) asserted that remuneration, encompassing not only base salary but also bonuses and other financial incentives, was a crucial factor in employee satisfaction. Kapoor (2023) highlighted the necessity of addressing wage concerns through transparent communication and regular wage reviews to build trust and reduce dissatisfaction. Salary equity, emphasized by Rodrigo et al. (2022), ensured employees perceived their pay as fair compared to their peers, fostering a sense of fairness and reducing feelings of inequality. Additionally, Saunders (2023) underscored the significance of supportive supervisory relationships, where supervisors provided guidance, recognized achievements, and supported career development, thus creating a

positive work environment. Collectively, these factors contributed to a motivated and satisfied workforce, resulting in better and higher-quality service delivery.

1.2 Labor Cost

Table 1.3

Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency in Selected Quick-Service Restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Labor Cost

Indicators in terms of Labor cost	(\bar{X}) Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Adequate staffing levels are maintained at budgeted labor costs.	3.01	Efficient	2.5
2. The team leader and agency crew show signs of willingness to offer cost-saving suggestions to the QSR management.	3.04	Efficient	1
3. The agency crew members display a strong eagerness to enhance their skills and increase productivity.	3.00	Efficient	4.5
4. The team leader is reliable in creating the agency crews' schedule to minimize overtime costs.	2.96	Efficient	7
5. The team leader is proficient in performance management of agency crew members to maintain an optimal level of mastery.	2.92	Efficient	9
6. The team leader shows capability in handling performance-based incentives that can motivate employees to increase productivity and reduce labor costs.	2.99	Efficient	6
7. The team leader shows eagerness to mobilize the agency crew to minimize the wastage.	2.95	Efficient	8
8. The agency crew demonstrates stewardship by implementing cost-saving measures related to labor cost management	2.86	Efficient	10
9. The training costs for newly deployed agency crew members fall within the allocated labor cost budget.	3.01	Efficient	2.5
10. The team leader is capable of managing the labor cost budget on a daily basis.	3.00	Efficient	4.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	2.97	Efficient	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Efficient 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Efficient
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Efficient 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Efficient

The job contractors in selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by their managers in Laguna in terms of Labor cost were Efficient (2.97). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Efficient. Furthermore, the indicator “The team leader and agency crew show signs of willingness to offer cost-saving suggestions to the QSR management.” had the highest computed mean of 3.04 meanwhile, the indicator “The agency crew demonstrates stewardship by implementing cost-saving measures related to labor cost management.” had the lowest computed mean of 2.86.

It conveys that agency team leaders are willing to provide insights and suggest action plans related to labor cost optimization. However, despite their clear intent and initiative, a gap remains in the actual execution of labor cost-saving measures. As representatives of the agency, team leaders are granted authority over control and supervision. Therefore, investing in their empowerment to effectively manage the performance of job contractor members and oversee the implementation of labor cost-saving initiatives can enhance the efficiency and productivity of the agency workforce.

Overall, the assessment highlights a positive foundation of efficiency, with opportunities for further improvement in practical application. This aligned with the findings of Kocerova et al. (2023) and Xu et al. (2022) both emphasized the importance of leveraging new technologies, such as digital systems for labor monitoring and performance tracking, to streamline operations and reduce costs. In a competitive industry where labor cost management was key to profitability, integrating advanced technologies into daily operations enhanced workforce efficiency, lowered operational overheads, and allowed businesses to remain agile and responsive to market demands. From a different perspective, Kartika and Oktarini (2022) highlighted the significant impact of operational costs on labor productivity, underscoring the importance of balancing expenses with output quality.

Research Question 2. What is the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by its managers in Laguna in terms of Responsiveness, Quality of Work, and Cost-effectiveness?

2.1 Responsiveness

The productivity level of selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by its managers in Laguna in terms of Responsiveness was Productive (3.03). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Productive. Furthermore, the indicator “They show signs of involvement with their team leader and agency crew.” had the highest computed mean of 3.20 meanwhile, the indicator “They identify and address issues before they escalate.” had the lowest computed mean of 2.89.

It indicates that managers assess the QSRs' productivity level in responsiveness as productive, reflecting a consistent and commendable level of attentiveness and involvement from the agency partner. The active participation of job contractors' team leaders and agency crews emerges as a key strength, showcasing strong engagement and collaboration. However, their ability to identify and address minor non-conformities to standard before escalation is identified as an area for improvement. Enhancing the team leaders' capabilities in control and supervision is crucial to addressing this gap. Overall, the job contractors demonstrate a notable commitment to responsiveness, but further development in handling and resolving minor non-conformities to standard procedures could significantly enhance their performance.

Table 2.1

Level of Productivity of Selected Quick-Service Restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Responsiveness

Indicators in terms of Responsiveness	(\bar{X}) Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. They respond promptly to requests from restaurant management.	3.05	Productive	3.5
2. They communicate regularly with restaurant staff regarding operational needs.	2.99	Productive	7.5
3. They demonstrate flexibility in adjusting to changes in the restaurant's requirements.	2.95	Productive	9
4. They identify and address issues before they escalate.	2.89	Productive	10
5. They provide timely updates on the progress of assigned tasks.	2.99	Productive	7.5
6. They are accessible and available to address urgent issues or emergencies.	3.04	Productive	5
7. They are trusted by the management to handle tasks assigned to them.	3.03	Productive	6
8. They maintain open lines of communication with all stakeholders involved.	3.05	Productive	3.5
9. They respond promptly to requests, concern from the agency crew.	3.08	Productive	2
10. They show signs of involvement with their team leader and agency crew.	3.20	Productive	1
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.03	Productive	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree / Highly Productive 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree / Slightly Productive
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree / Productive 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree / Not Productive

The level of responsiveness played a critical role in business operations, as highlighted by Ricardo (2022) in his study on the correlation between responsiveness, efficiency, and accountability. This was advantageous for the principal, as it helped ensure customer satisfaction and operational efficiency, which, according to Morinaga et al. (2022), were directly linked to increased client satisfaction and customer loyalty. While empowering the job contractor, Saunders (2023) narrated that insufficient training could result in ineffective and inconsistent supervisory methods, leading to low job satisfaction among supervisees and inconsistent adherence to treatment protocols.

2.2 Quality of Work

The Productivity of Selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Quality of Work was Productive (3.08). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Productive. Furthermore, the indicator “They consistently produce work of high quality.” had the highest computed mean of 3.18 meanwhile, the indicator “They consistently take ownership of assigned tasks.” had the lowest computed mean of 2.86.

Table 2.2

Level of Productivity of Selected Quick-Service Restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Quality of Work

Indicators in terms of Quality of work	(\bar{X}) Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. They consistently produce work of high quality.	3.18	Productive	1
2. They ensure task completion.	3.01	Productive	9
3. They adhere to established standards and procedures.	3.09	Productive	6
4. They continuously seek ways to improve work outcomes.	3.12	Productive	3
5. They are satisfied with the amount of workload given by the QSR	3.08	Productive	7
6. They consistently demonstrate attention to detail in all aspects of their work.	3.07	Productive	8
7. They consistently take ownership of assigned tasks.	2.86	Productive	10
8. They effectively manage resources for optimal outcomes.	3.11	Productive	4.5
9. They appear to be helpful in meeting customer expectations.	3.14	Productive	2
10. They are attentive to the customer's needs.	3.11	Productive	4.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.08	Productive	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree / Highly Productive 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree / Slightly Productive
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree / Productive 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree / Not Productive

This suggests that managers perceive the QSRs' productivity related to work quality as productive, manifesting that agency partners are highly engaged and committed to delivering quality output. This demonstrates that job contractors consistently strive to provide excellent service and meet the principal's quality standards, despite productivity concerns of QSR operations. Their efforts effectively meet customer expectations, reflecting a strong dedication to customer satisfaction and a proactive approach to continuous improvement. However, enhancing task ownership and responsibility could further elevate their performance. When job contractors fully embrace responsibility for their tasks, they become more proactive in problem-solving and maintaining high-quality results. Clear expectations, proper training, and a degree of independence foster a sense of pride in their roles. Team leaders reinforce this by supervising effectively and serving as role models. Cultivating a culture of accountability contributes to improved customer satisfaction, streamlined operations, and strengthened relationships between contractors and management.

To elaborate further, Ubaidillah and Parlinda (2023) highlighted several factors that contributed to this, including job training, motivation, work environment, role overload, and work-life balance. These elements helped job contractors assist the QSR in achieving consumer satisfaction. Udayalakshmi and Sridevi (2023) elaborated that service quality was a measure of how well an organization met customer expectations; therefore, consumers ultimately dictated the level of quality required in the QSR industry. It was impressive that job contractors continuously sought ways to improve their work outcomes. With the ever-changing market demands, it was encouraging to see job contractors embracing continuous improvement. For example, Neacșu and Tulbure (2023) noted the growing interest in healthy eating while Udayalakshmi and Sridevi (2023) discussed how

disruptive technologies like artificial intelligence and automation were impacting service quality.

2.3 Cost-Effectiveness

Table 2.3

Level of Productivity of Selected Quick-Service Restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Cost-Effectiveness

Indicators in terms of Cost-effectiveness	(\bar{X}) Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The job contractor provides value for the cost of their services.	3.18	Productive	2
2. The job contractor helps the QSR optimize resource utilization.	3.09	Productive	5.5
3. The agency crew contributes to the overall profitability of the QSR.	3.00	Productive	8
4. The team leader is consistent in balancing labor cost reduction with maintaining service quality within the QSR	2.91	Productive	10
5. The job contractors consistently adhere to the SLA, particularly in situations where costs are incurred that affect financial performance in the store.	2.96	Productive	9
6. The agency crew is interested in learning new tasks or assignments in the QSR.	3.03	Productive	7
7. The job contractor is transparent in billing practices.	3.19	Productive	1
8. Agency crew members prioritize delivering quality without compromising on cost.	3.12	Productive	3
9. The job contractor consistently offers flexible schedules to meet the QSRs' manpower demands.	3.11	Productive	4
10. The job contractor reduces the administrative task of the management team as such associated with the agency crew training	3.09	Productive	5.5
GENERAL ASSESSMENT	3.07	Productive	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree / Highly Productive 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree / Slightly Productive
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree / Productive 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree / Not Productive

The productivity of selected quick-service restaurants as assessed by its Managers in Laguna in terms of Cost-effectiveness was Productive (3.07). All indicators were verbally interpreted as Productive. Furthermore, the indicator “The job contractor is transparent in billing practices.” had the highest computed mean of 3.19 meanwhile, the indicator “The team leader is consistent in balancing labor cost reduction with maintaining service quality within the QSR.” had the lowest computed mean of 2.91.

It entails that the managers assess the QSRs’ productivity in dealing with cost-effectiveness as productive, showing that transparency in billing practices stands out as a key strength, highlighting the contractors' commitment to clear and honest financial dealings. These practices minimize potential disputes in QSR contracting processes. Additionally, ensuring the accurate interpretation of periodical financial reports is considered vital, as these reports serve as essential tools for the management team, acting as the principal's representatives and decision-makers. Conducting cost analyses

enables the management team to develop relevant action plans to address pressing issues effectively.

On the other hand, team leaders' ability to work within the labor cost budget while maintaining service quality receives the lowest rating, highlighting an area for improvement in balancing cost efficiency and service excellence. While job contractors display commendable cost-effectiveness, particularly in financial transparency, enhancing team leaders' capacity to manage labor costs without compromising quality is identified as crucial. Strengthening this skill is essential for sustaining operational excellence and competitiveness in the dynamic QSR industry.

These findings aligned with the study by Binik-Thomas (2022), which emphasized the importance of establishing transparent expectations, implementing pre-approved protocols, and delegating authority within teams. In terms of balancing quality and cost, Adelia and Aprianingsih (2023) highlighted that enhancing output quality had to align with business profitability to ensure sustainable growth. Moreover, all strategies needed to be monitored, as Mzughulga and Moiseeva (2023) underscored the significance of direct labor cost monitoring and production efficiency in optimizing costs.

Research Question 3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of job contractor’s efficiency and the level of productivity of selected Quick-Service Restaurants in Laguna?

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Job Contractors’ Efficiency and Level of Productivity of Selected Quick-Service Restaurants in Laguna

Level of Job Contractor’s Efficiency	Productivity level	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Turnover Rate	Responsiveness	.730**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Quality of work	.813**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Cost-effectiveness	.795**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
Job Satisfaction	Responsiveness	.820**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Quality of work	.786**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Cost-effectiveness	.835**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
Labor Cost	Responsiveness	.864**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Quality of work	.926**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o
	Cost-effectiveness	.922**	.000	Significant	Reject H _o

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

There was **significant relationship** between the level of job contractors’ efficiency and the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna. Furthermore, the r values were interpreted as **high positive to very high positive (.730 to .926)** to correlate the level of efficiency among the job contractors and the level of productivity of

QSRs. The computed probability values of **.000** were lesser than the level of significance ($P < 0.05$); thus, the **null hypothesis was rejected**.

This study concludes that improving job contractors' efficiency in areas such as turnover rate, job satisfaction, and labor cost significantly influences the level of productivity of QSRs, particularly in responsiveness, quality of work, and cost-effectiveness. These improvements directly influence the overall operational success of QSRs. Efficient job contractors help increase productivity levels, emphasizing the mutual dependency between QSRs as principals and job contractors as their agencies.

This conclusion was supported by the findings of Ravari et al. (2020), who emphasized that selecting the right job contractor was a crucial decision for the principal, as it significantly influenced the success of the project and overall business operations.

Similarly, Madhavi and Mehrotra (2020) highlighted that an organization's success depended on the trust and competence of its workforce, including job contractors. They emphasized the importance of competence management, recommending continuous training and skill development programs to enhance employee confidence and sustain organizational efficiency. Furthermore, Chico et al. (2023) underscored that organizational culture played a vital role in employee performance within the QSR industry, stressing the need for alignment between the principal and the agency's culture or the agency's ability to adapt effectively.

Research Question 4. Does the level of efficiency among the job contractors significantly impact the level of productivity of selected quick-service restaurants in Laguna?

4.1 Responsiveness

Table 4.1

Regression Analysis on the Impact of Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency in the Level of Productivity of QSRs in terms of Responsiveness

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error					
(Constant)	-.071	.234		-.304	.762		
Turnover Rate	-.028	.114	-.025	-.241	.810	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Job Satisfaction	.423	.145	.333	2.918	.005	Reject Ho	Significant
Labor Cost	.617	.114	.606	5.425	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: Responsiveness

R – Square = .778 F-value = 81.809
 Adjusted R Square = .769 Significance = .000

Regression analysis disclosed that the efficiency level such as job satisfaction and labor cost among the job contractors significantly impacted the level of productivity of selected QSRs in terms of responsiveness at **77.80%**. Furthermore, the probability value of labor cost and job satisfaction were **0.000** and **0.005** respectively, lesser than the level of significance at .05, thus **rejecting the null hypothesis**.

The study denotes that job satisfaction and labor costs play a significant role in the overall performance of a QSR business, particularly in terms of responsiveness. These aspects directly influence how efficiently job contractors address the needs of agency crews, team leaders, and the operational demands of the QSR. When contractors are highly responsive, employees feel valued and supported, leading to improved job satisfaction. This encourages agency crew members to stay, which ultimately decreases the attrition rate, reduces unproductive man-hours caused by frequent training, and eliminates unnecessary labor costs. Additionally, having a flexible job contractor who can make adjustments, align with, and adapt to the ever-changing demands of QSRs, especially in this VUCA (volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous) world, proves to be highly advantageous for the QSR.

The prompt resolution of issues boosted job satisfaction and optimized labor costs by increasing productivity and minimizing unproductive man-hours during training. These factors contributed to improved profitability and the overall performance of the QSR business. The findings of this study aligned with Morinaga et al. (2022) suggested that enhanced responsiveness could improve customer satisfaction and operational efficiency. Similarly, Raghuram and Saleeshya (2021) emphasized that improving responsiveness could enhance customer service, operational efficiency, and overall profitability.

4.2 Quality of Work

Table 4.2

Regression Analysis on the Impact of Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency in the Level of Productivity of QSRs in terms of Quality of Work

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	.422	.162		2.604	.011		
Turnover Rate	.226	.079	.226	2.863	.006	Reject Ho	Significant
Job Satisfaction	-.085	.100	-.074	-.853	.397	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Labor Cost	.752	.079	.807	9.562	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: Quality of Work

R – Square = .873 F-value = 160.471
Adjusted R Square = .868 Significance = .000

Regression Analysis revealed that the efficiency level such as turnover rate and labor cost among the job contractors significantly impacted the level of productivity of the selected QSRs in terms of quality of work at **87.30%**. Furthermore, the probability value of labor and turnover rate were **0.000** and **0.006** respectively, lesser than the level of significance at .05, thus **rejecting the null hypothesis**.

The study suggests that turnover rates and labor costs play a significant role in the overall performance of a QSR business, particularly in terms of quality of work. High-quality work contributes to smoother operations, better customer service, fewer mistakes, and fewer customer complaints, all of which lead to lower turnover rates among job contractor members. If they are confident in the quality of their work and see positive outcomes, they are more likely to stay in their roles. Likewise, it contributes to increasing the level of mastery among agency crew. This reduces the need for constant recruitment and training, which can be costly for the QSR business.

Conversely, poor-quality work—such as mistakes in orders, slow service, or inconsistent food quality—can lead to dissatisfaction among both job contractor members and customers. This dissatisfaction increases turnover rates as job contractor members may leave due to stress or frustration, which in turn raises recruitment and training costs. Additionally, errors in service or food preparation that led to customer complaints need extra effort and resources to resolve, further increasing expenses including labor costs. Therefore, ensuring high-quality work not only enhances job contractor member retention but also helps control operational expenses, contributing to a more efficient and cost-effective business model.

Improved work quality promotes QSR's brand image and reputation, strengthens partnerships with job contractors, fosters job security, and reduces turnover intentions. It also boosts job satisfaction by enabling employees to support their families, promoting pride and happiness. Additionally, increased levels of productivity and optimized labor costs drive profitability, enhancing overall business performance.

This was aligned with the study of Ubaidillah and Parlinda (2023) wherein they enumerated factors such as job training, work motivation, work environment, role overload, love of money, empowerment, work engagement, happiness, and work-life balance that could impact the quality of work. Similarly, Ghosh et al. (2023) revealed that service quality and employee attitudes positively influence customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions.

4.3 Cost Effectiveness

Regression analysis determined that the efficiency level in terms of labor cost among the job contractors significantly impacted the productivity level of the QSRs in terms of cost-effectiveness at **86.50%**. Furthermore, the probability value of labor cost was **0.000**, lesser than the level of significance at .05, thus **rejecting the null hypothesis**.

Table 4.3

Regression Analysis on the Impact of Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency in the Level of productivity of QSRs in terms of Cost Effectiveness

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	Decisions	Remarks
	B	Std. Error					
(Constant)	.295	.162		1.821	.073		
Turnover Rate	.089	.079	.092	1.131	.262	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Job Satisfaction	.186	.100	.166	1.860	.067	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Labor Cost	.641	.079	.710	8.156	.000	Reject Ho	Significant

Dependent Variable: Cost Effectiveness

R – Square	=	.865	F-value	=	149.695
Adjusted R Square	=	.859	Significance	=	.000

The study implies labor cost plays a significant role in the overall performance of a QSR business, particularly in terms of cost-effectiveness. Profitability is the cornerstone of business survival, sustainability, and growth, enabling QSRs to explore new opportunities and expand their market presence. Labor costs significantly influence cost-effectiveness, representing a substantial portion of the variable cost in the QSRs' financial condition. By optimizing labor costs, the business not only enhances its financial stability but also positions itself for future growth and expansion.

This was aligned with the findings of Xu et al. (2022), Kartika and Oktarini (2022), and Kocerova et al. (2023), all of whom highlighted a strong relationship between operational costs and labor productivity. These studies emphasized that adopting lean practices and efficient management strategies significantly reduced costs while improving overall performance. Therefore, ensuring cost-effectiveness in labor management was essential for QSRs to maintain a competitive edge and ensure long-term success.

Research Question 5. Based on the findings of the study, what training and development program may be proposed for job contractors catering QSRs in Laguna?

As a result of this study, a training and development program was proposed for job contractor agencies serving selected QSRs in Laguna. This program aimed to improve the efficiency of job contractors, thereby helping management increase the level of productivity of the QSR. This training and development program initiative may give a positive impact on the business performance of both parties, particularly in terms of operational efficiency leading to strong partnership.

Table 5.1

Proposed Action Plan to Improve the Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency in Selected QSRs' in Laguna in terms of Turnover Rate, Job Satisfaction and Labor Cost

General Objective : To contribute to the development of all agency team leaders to improve their business performance within the QSR.

KEY AREAS	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES	ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME/ FREQUENCY / MODALITY	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Turn-over rate	Leadership	Leadership workshop *Conduct sessions on communication, decision making and conflict resolution.	Role-playing scenarios where team leaders must resolve workplace conflicts or make critical decisions	1 day / semestral Classroom set-up	Collaboration of agency partner and management / HR department	85% of participants will be able to apply the learning and document a scenario as their output
	To enhance leadership ability to inspire, guide, and influence the team effectively.	Shadowing / Mentorship *Allow team leaders to observe how to perform his roles effectively and efficiently.	Create a mentorship program to help them perform their assigned task effectively and efficiently.	1 week / annually On field		80% of participants will be able to complete the mentorship program.
		Periodical Performance Assessment. *Seek feedback from superior.	Practice soliciting feedback during periodical meetings.	4 hours / monthly Meeting set-up		90% of participants will be able to solicit and discuss their performance.
Job Satisfaction	Proactiveness	Scenario-Based Training *Simulate workplace productivity concerns requiring proactive solutions	Let the team leader solve a hypothetical issue like short in staff, complaints from members then present their solutions	4 hours / monthly Classroom set-up	Collaboration of agency partner and management / HR department	90% of participants will be able to handle and document the application in actual scenario
	To encourage team leaders to anticipate productivity concerns, identify opportunities and take initiative.	Opportunity Spotting *Train team leaders to identify growth or improvement areas.	Conduct a "gap analysis" of their team's operations and propose initiatives.	1 week / annually On field		80% of participants will be able to handle and document the application in actual scenario
		Innovation Challenges *Reward team leaders for presenting innovative ideas to improve operations.	Host a periodical meeting where colleagues propose new ideas to enhance productivity or morale.	4 hours / monthly Meeting se-up		90% of participants will be able to handle and document the application in actual scenario
Labor Cost	Ownership	Task Ownership Exercises *Assign team leaders responsibility for a project or initiative from start to finish.	Develop and present a plan for improving a specific area of assignment within the operation, with measurable outcomes.	3 months Project -based	Collaboration of agency partner and management / HR department	50% of participants will be able to develop a project related and aligned to his duties and responsibilities
	To foster a sense of accountability and responsibility for achieving team and organization al goals.	Accountability Training *Train team leaders on setting goals and owning their outcomes.	Use historical data or case study where ownership influenced success or failure to discuss actionable lessons.	3 months Project -based		50% of participants will be able to develop a project related and aligned to his duties and responsibilities
		Reflection Workshops *Help team leaders reflect on their successes and areas for improvement.	Write a journal entry analyzing the results of a recent leadership decision.	3 hours / semestral Classroom set-up		30% participants will be able to share their most impactful decision for the month.

To effectively enhance leadership abilities that inspire, guide, and influence teams, conducting leadership workshops focusing on communication, decision-making, and conflict resolution is essential. For instance, sessions could involve role-playing scenarios where team leaders must resolve workplace conflicts or make critical decisions. Conducted in a classroom set-up, these workshops, in collaboration with agency partners and the management/HR department, expected to enable 85% of participants can apply their learning and document a scenario as their output. Furthermore, implementing a shadowing/mentorship program would allow team leaders to observe and perform their roles efficiently. This hands-on experience, conducted on-field annually for a week, is projected to result in 80% of participants completing the program successfully. Lastly, periodical performance assessments through monthly meetings where feedback is solicited from superiors can enhance team leaders' performance. A structured meeting set-up is expected to enable 90% of participants to discuss and evaluate their performance effectively.

Encouraging proactiveness among team leaders involves anticipating productivity concerns, identifying opportunities, and taking initiative. Scenario-based training is an effective method, where team leaders simulate workplace productivity concerns and propose proactive solutions. Conducted in a classroom set-up monthly, this training, in collaboration with agency partners and management/HR department, aims for 90% of participants to handle and document their application in actual scenarios. Another approach is opportunity spotting, where team leaders are trained to identify growth or improvement areas by conducting a "gap analysis" of their team's operations and proposing initiatives. This annual, on-field exercise should result in 80% of participants successfully applying and documenting their learnings. Innovation challenges can further motivate team leaders by rewarding them for presenting new ideas to enhance productivity or morale. By hosting periodical meetings where colleagues propose improvements, the goal is for 90% of participants to effectively document and apply their innovations.

Fostering a sense of accountability and responsibility among team leaders involves assigning them ownership of projects or initiatives. Task ownership exercises, where leaders are responsible for a project from start to finish, can significantly improve team and organizational goals. For example, team leaders could develop and present a plan for enhancing a specific operational area with measurable outcomes. Conducted over three months in a project-based set-up, in collaboration with agency partners and management/HR department, the objective is for 50% of participants to develop projects aligned with their duties and responsibilities. This approach ensures that team leaders are not only accountable but also actively contribute to the organization's success.

Findings

1. The Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency in selected Quick-Service Restaurants in Laguna in terms of:

1.1. Turnover rate

It had a general assessment of 3.05 which was verbally interpreted as Efficient.

1.2. Job Satisfaction

It had a general assessment of 3.19 which was verbally interpreted as Efficient.

1.3. Labor Cost

It had a general assessment of 2.97 which was verbally interpreted as Efficient.

2. The Level of Productivity of selected Quick-Service Restaurants as in Laguna in terms of:

2.1. Responsiveness

It had a general assessment of 3.03 which was verbally interpreted as Productive.

2.2 Quality of work

It had a general assessment of 3.08 which was verbally interpreted as Productive.

2.3 Cost-effectiveness

It had a general assessment of 3.07 which was verbally interpreted as Productive.

3. Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency and Level of Productivity of Selected Quick-Service Restaurants in Laguna.

There was a significant relationship between the level of job contractors' efficiency in terms of turnover rate, job satisfaction, and labor cost, and the level of productivity of selected QSRs in terms of responsiveness, quality of work, and cost-effectiveness. The r values .730 to .926 were interpreted as having a high positive to very high positive correlation between the level of efficiency among the job contractors and the level of productivity of QSRs. The generated probability values were all less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

4. Regression Analysis on the Level of Job Contractors' Efficiency and Level of Productivity of selected Quick-Service Restaurants in Laguna.

The level of job contractors' efficiency, such as job satisfaction and labor cost, significantly impacted the level of productivity in terms of Responsiveness by 77.80%. The probability values of .000 and .005 were less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. On the other hand, the turnover rate had a probability value of 0.810.

The level of job contractors' efficiency, such as turnover rate and labor cost, significantly impacted the level of productivity in terms of quality of work by 87.30%. The probability values of .000 and .006 were less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. On the other hand, job satisfaction had a probability value of 0.397.

The level of job contractors' efficiency, such as labor cost, significantly impacted the level of productivity in terms of cost-effectiveness by 86.50%. The probability value of .000 was less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis. On the other hand, turnover rate and job satisfaction had probability values of 0.262 and 0.067, respectively.

5. Based on the findings of the study, what training and development programs may be proposed to improve the efficiency of job contractors catering to QSRs within Laguna?

A training and development program was proposed to the job contractor and the HR department of QSRs handling agency partner. This training and development program may help to improve the skills and develop capabilities of the agency team leader necessary to perform his role effectively.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions may be derived:

1. That the demonstrated job stability significantly contributes to the overall satisfaction and sense of security of the agency crew. Moreover, the active involvement of agency team leaders in providing valuable insights and actionable plans optimizes labor costs, thereby enhancing the efficiency of the job contractor system. This efficiency reduces avoidable costs caused by frequent training and hiring while simultaneously improving the level of mastery among agency crew members. This enhanced mastery ensures consistency in delivering quality outputs. However, despite these strengths, there are still identified areas for improvement to further enhance the efficiency of job contractors.

2. That the job contractors exhibit strong engagement with team leaders and agency crew, demonstrating a commitment to achieving quality results. Transparency in billing practices emerges as a significant strength, reflecting the contractors' dedication to clear and honest financial transactions. These practices contribute positively to the overall productivity of quick-service restaurants.

3. That as the efficiency levels improve, the productivity of QSRs also increases. Empowering team leaders and agency crew through continuous collaboration and regular updates enables them to adapt effectively to changes in consumer demand. This adaptability, particularly in maintaining quality standards, is integral to the success of the business partnership.

4. That the higher job satisfaction and optimized labor costs result in a more effective response to operational demands. Furthermore, lower turnover rates and well-managed labor costs contribute to a higher level of mastery among crew members, thereby improving work quality. Labor costs are critical in determining the cost-effectiveness of job contractors, as higher costs can negatively affect overall efficiency.

5. Based on the findings of the study, a training and development program for agency crew team leaders is needed. The opportunities for improvement include the implementation of the program, achieving a cost-quality equilibrium, enhancing leadership, fostering loyalty and ownership, and improving proactiveness in correcting adherence to standard operating procedures and responsiveness to individual concerns. Since agency team leaders are accountable for wages, control, and supervision,

empowering them in these areas can have a significant positive impact on the overall performance of the job contractor.

Recommendations

This study identified the efficiency of job contractors catering to selected QSRs in Laguna and its impact on the level of productivity of the operation. Based on the findings, the following key recommendations are proposed:

1. The performance of job contractors plays a crucial role in driving the success of QSR operations. To ensure a high level of efficiency, it is essential for job contractors, in collaboration with QSR management, to focus on key areas for improvement, such as strengthening members' loyalty, promptly addressing member concerns, and effectively implementing cost-saving initiatives. Supporting these efforts with targeted training and development programs may further enhance their effectiveness. Recommended initiatives include leadership workshops to equip team leaders with essential people management and decision-making skills, shadowing and mentorship programs to promote on-the-job learning and knowledge transfer, and periodic performance assessments to consistently evaluate and improve individual and team performance. By prioritizing these strategies, job contractors may significantly enhance their contributions to QSR operations, foster stronger partnerships, and drive mutual success.

2. The productivity level of the QSRs is largely influenced by the performance of job contractors. To increase the level of productivity, it is recommended that management implement the proposed training and development program, designed to enhance the leadership skills of agency team leaders. The key areas for improvement should include ensuring job contractors' adherence to company standard procedures, fostering a sense of ownership and accountability, and strengthening team leaders' ability to manage labor costs while maintaining service quality.

3. The relationship between job contractors' efficiency and the level of productivity of QSRs is established in this study. It is recommended to empower the team leader in the aspect of agency crew performance management, leadership skills development, ownership and accountability, and labor cost management orientation. This may be supported by periodical assessments of team leader performance and coaching.

4. This study recommends implementing programs that boost job contractor satisfaction, such as recognition initiatives and open communication channels, to enhance responsiveness and overall morale. Promoting loyalty through career development opportunities and assignment rotation plans helps reduce turnover and improves work quality. Involving team leaders in labor cost management ensures a balanced approach to operational efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and employee well-being. These strategies foster a more engaged and productive workforce.

5. This training and development program aims to address the critical issues and concerns related to the level of productivity of QSR operations as a business. By enhancing control and supervision, the program seeks to empower agency team leaders

in areas such as agency crew performance management, leadership skills development, proactiveness, ownership and accountability, and labor cost management. To ensure its effectiveness, it is strongly recommended that the program be supported by periodic performance assessments and coaching for agency team leaders, providing ongoing guidance and improvement. Furthermore, the program should be regularly revisited and updated to maintain its relevance and alignment with current operational needs. By doing so, it may enhance the efficiency of job contractors, increase productivity, and adapt to the dynamic demands of QSR operations. Ultimately, this program may improve responsiveness, elevate quality standards, and enhance cost-effectiveness, leading to better overall business performance and operational success.

6. This study focuses exclusively on two QSR brands in Laguna, but future research could expand its scope to include all QSR brands in the research locale. The structure of this study may serve as a framework for broader research. The potential of uncovering additional factors such as psychological stress of managers and crew, credentials of agency partners, and the like that may influence the relationship between job contractors' efficiency and the productivity level of QSRs in achieving operational excellence.

Moreover, future researchers are encouraged to include the perspectives of the agency crew in their data collection process. By incorporating insights from both agency crew and management, future studies could provide a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the overall situation, yielding a clearer picture of the dynamics at play.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical considerations were taken into account since this study necessitated the involvement of representatives from the principal. Addressing these issues was paramount to safeguard the privacy and security of respondents. Key ethical concerns, including consent, confidentiality, and data protection, were thoroughly addressed throughout the research process. Clear and comprehensive communication of all essential details was ensured, aiming to obtain consent from both the respondents and at the same time from the authorized personnel from the company's human resources department. Respondents were provided with clear instructions and essential information to understand their role in the study process. They were assured that their data would be handled with utmost confidentiality, and all respondents were treated equitably. Consequently, only pertinent information necessary to address the specific research questions was shared.

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